

Detection Of Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy In Type–II Diabetes Population

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A B S T R A C T

Background:

Diabetes Mellitus causes chronic hyperglycemia leading to nerve damage and Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, presenting with pain, sensory loss, weakness, and balance impairment. Early stages are often asymptomatic, causing underdiagnosis. Urban diabetics in Pune are high risk. The Toronto Clinical Neuropathy Scoring Scale enables simple, cost-effective physiotherapy-based screening for early detection and disability prevention.

Method:

227 diabetic patients from Wise Diabetes Clinic and Research Center, Pune, ages 50 to 70 years, participated in this cross-sectional observational study. Participants had to have at least five years of diabetes exposure. Common symptoms like pain, tingling, numbness, weakness and ataxia were questioned about and sensations like pin-prick, touch, temperature, vibration and position were evaluated along with examining the integrity of knee and ankle reflexes.

Results:

Among 227 participants, most were aged 56–58 years, with diabetes onset commonly at 47–52 years and duration of 5–14 years. Gender distribution was almost equal, and 42% were overweight. Neuropathy affected 61.2% of diabetics, predominantly moderate to severe.

Lower-limb pain, sensory loss, and ataxia were common and symmetrical. Neuropathy was more frequent and severe among patients not adhering to regular medication.

Conclusion:

Diabetic peripheral neuropathy is highly prevalent (61.2%) in Pune type 2 diabetic population, with 26.4% severe cases. Poor glycemic control, obesity, long disease duration, and non-adherence are key risk factors. The Toronto Clinical Scoring System supports early screening, enabling multidisciplinary management to prevent progression, ulcers, and amputations.

Keywords:

Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, Toronto Clinical Scoring Scale, Pathophysiology of Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy, Pune Population

INTRODUCTION:

Type-II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), one of the most common metabolic disorders, is caused by a combination of two primary factors: defective insulin secretion by pancreatic β -cells and the inability of insulin-sensitive tissues to respond appropriately to insulin. Insulin release and its activity are essential processes for glucose homeostasis to be obtained. Defects attained in any of these mechanisms involved can lead to a metabolic imbalance responsible for the development of the disease.^[1]

Diabetes mellitus is a common non-communicable metabolic disorder and albeit being idiopathic, it has been associated with several vascular and nonvascular complications. Neuropathy is perhaps the most crucial complication as it can cause severe, devastating complications that quell disability and quality of life if not diagnosed early. Neuropathy is a common microvascular complication type which makes it one of the most common problems in diabetes alongside peripheral vascular disease; the most leading cause of non-traumatic lower limb amputations are because they have these two complications.^[2]

Definition Neuropathy is not a single disease, but rather an umbrella term which describes the conditions with different disorders. These can be focal or diffuse, proximal or distal and small- versus large-fibre nerve dysfunction. Diabetic sensorimotor polyneuropathy is the most frequent form of diabetic neuropathy (also referred to as diabetic peripheral

neuropathy [DPN]) and which is symptomatic (e.g. paresthesia, numbness, pain or allodynia) contributing significantly to morbidity. Chronic hyperglycemia is the main cause of the initiation of various metabolic events underlying diabetic peripheral neuropathy. A mass number of studies suggests that insulin or C peptide deficiencies or both contribute highly to severe diabetic peripheral neuropathy. A combination of direct axonal injury caused by the metabolic consequences of hyperglycemic insulin resistance, endothelial injury, toxic adiposity, and microvascular dysfunctions leads to nerve ischemia. Diabetes causes alterations in endothelial derived relaxing factor (EDRF) and functional deficits in nitric oxide (NO) resulting in microvascular reactivity and structural microangiopathy, which adds to the worsening of DPN.^[2]

Normal healthy nerves are supplied with rich blood supply from the neural vasculature also known as vasa nervorum. With diabetic peripheral neuropathy, the vascular changes include increased permeability, increased vasoconstriction, and decreased blood flow, which in turn appear to cause motor and sensory-nerve-fibre degeneration.^[3]

One of the major hallmarks for diabetic peripheral neuropathy is axonal atrophy. Diabetes mellitus causes impaired peripheral nerve regeneration. Thus the characteristic features for diabetic neuropathy are slower conduction velocity, impairment of axonal transport, axonal atrophy, and reduced capacity for nerve regeneration. Proper nerve functioning is highly depended on the integrity of the axonal cytoskeleton and particularly on the neurofilaments which are inevitably damaged in chronic diabetes mellitus.^[4]

The general prevalence of DPN is 45.45%. As age increased the frequency of neuropathy also raised, up to 72.7% in more than 60 years versus only 23.5% when ≤ 40 years. Furthermore; the trend of direct relationship between DPN with longer duration of DM was also statistically significant as more than 55% patients have >5 years disease. The most prominent symptoms of diabetic peripheral neuropathy is loss of pain perception and unsteadiness, weakness and ataxia, which compromise activities of daily living (ADLs). Additionally, there is a marked loss in vibration perception and presence of deep seated gnawing pain (A-fibre). People with DPN and impaired vibration perception are 15 times more likely to fall than people without neuropathy.^[5]

Diabetes mellitus has numerous complications associated with it and one of the most distressing complications of diabetic peripheral neuropathy is Diabetic Foot Ulcer which

affects approximately 15% of the diabetic population. The classical triad for diabetic foot neuropathy is neuropathy, ischemia, and infection. The impaired metabolic mechanisms in diabetes mellitus cause an increased risk of infection and poor wound healing capacity. This occurs due to series of mechanisms which include decreased cell growth factor response, diminished peripheral blood circulation and decreased local angiogenesis causing the feet to be influenced by damage to peripheral nerves, peripheral vascular disease, ulcerations, deformities, and gangrene.^[6,7]

Hyperglycemia induced microangiopathy induces low peripheral sensation and compensation of fine vasomotor control of the pedal circulation and the nerve innervations of small muscles of the foot. If the nerve gets damage, then a patient can very easily get any kind of minor injury without sensing it until an ulcer takes place. Patients with diabetes are at a higher risk of ulcer expansion due to reduced sensations in the leg. Diabetic patients are up to seven times more likely as compared with patients without neuropathy to have increased sensory loss. It is also associated with autonomic system functions which controls the microcirculation of skin thus affecting, among other things, the skin that can become dry and hyperkeratotic as well as friable, leading to infections. These changes contribute to gangrene, ulcers and limb loss.^[8]

Diabetes is a major risk factor for foot ulceration and protection of the high-risk diabetic foot by appropriate screening, education and intervention measures appears to reduce this risk in practice. Clinicians are the first line of defence & should screen all patients to identify ones at risk for foot ulceration. This includes a review of pertinent past history and identification of any present foot deformity, with special attention to testing for loss of protective sensation using a monofilament and perception of vibrations. Other useful screening tools might be the measurement of ABIs to look for peripheral vascular disease, making sure proper fitting shoes have been worn and plantar pressure is high if able.^[9]

Screening enables the clinician to place the patient in a risk category thereby determining what type of foot care interventions are required and information given to the patient on proper footwear, avoiding activities leading to higher pressures such as running or jumping and wearing appropriate shoes that would improve the load distribution.^[9] The 30-day mortality was as high as 30 per cent and over half the patients had died within one year of undergoing an amputation. There was a striking relationship between the mortality and age as well as pre-amputation morbidity.^[10] The mortality after BKA ranged from 40% to 82%

and after AKA from 40% to 90%. The risk factors included age, renal disease, proximal amputation, diabetes, and PVD.^[11]

Gold standard method for evaluation of diabetic peripheral neuropathy are: nerve conduction studies and skin biopsies, but they being costly and invasive techniques may have problem with their reproducibility as well as clinical applicability. Toronto Clinical Scoring System is a clinical measure of neuropathy and showed reasonable sensitivity while paralleling the invasive measures. The Toronto Clinical Scoring system was used to diagnose other Polyneuropathies as well and is proved to be a reliable tool with a sensitivity of 82 % and specificity of 87%.^[13]

The Toronto Clinical Scoring System employs basic neurological history and examination skills that are intended to be straightforward for practising clinicians. The elements of the Toronto CSS were determined based on expert local opinion for a definition agreed by consensus between neurologists and diabetologists. Questions on whether or not the pain is burning, stabbing, or shock-like (ie characteristic of neuropathic types) as well and if there is numbness; tingling; weakness in both feet; and symptoms similar to these noted anywhere else other than your hands culminated with an ambulatory instability question followed by a sensory test administered over the 1st toe. The end product, the clinical neuropathy score is a continuous variable ranging from 0 (no evidence of neuropathy) to 30 (indicating severe neuropathy).^[12,13,14]

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

To determine the prevalence of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in Type-II diabetic patients, a cross-sectional observational study was carried out. Based on self-reported symptoms and assessment of sensations, the study sought to forecast the possible risk of developing diabetic peripheral neuropathy. After receiving ethical approval from the institutional research committee and authorization from the relevant authorities, it was conducted over the course of four months, from March to June 2025, at Wise Diabetes Clinic and Research Center, Pune.

Male and female patients at Wise Diabetes Clinic and Research Center made up the research population. This group was chosen based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria which included patients between the ages 50-70 years, that should be exposed to diabetes for 5 years and more. Convenient sampling was used to choose 227 diabetic patients in total

depending on their availability and willingness to take part. Prior to data collection, each subject provided written informed consent. To gather information for clinical evaluation of diabetic peripheral neuropathy, demographics of age, gender, BMI, Random Blood Capillary Glucose measure, years of exposure to diabetes and adherence to medication was noted and then assessment using the Toronto Clinical Neuropathy Scoring System was conducted. Common symptoms that included pain, numbness, tingling, weakness, ataxia and upper-limb symptoms were questioned about, then assessment of the sensations of the great toe for touch, pain, temperature, vibration and position along with knee and ankle reflex elicitation were all covered in the scale. The total score of the TCNS was used to estimate the level of developed diabetic peripheral neuropathy. Each symptom was evaluated dichotomously as present/abnormal or absent/normal. In order to ensure proper understanding, the procedure and need of study was explained in the local language.

Microsoft Excel was used to enter the data into a master chart. The distribution of signs, symptoms and demographic characteristics were represented using descriptive statistics like frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

The study involved 227 patients from Wise Diabetes Clinic and Research Center, Pune. The participants ranged in age from 50 to 70, with a mean age of **60.49 ± 6.11 years**. Most of them were exposed to diabetes for **10.96 ± 6.01 years**, having the mean age of diabetes onset as **49.53 ± 4.91 years**. The cohort reveals a nearly equivalent distribution between genders, with 51% females and 49% males. The predominance of poor glycemic control in the study population, observed with the mean RBG of **204.3 ± 45.6 mg/dL** with 55% participants reporting regular medication intake and 45% participants not adhering to prescribed medications. The majority of participants had an overweight body mass index, with a mean of **27.87 ± 4.86 kg/m²**, suggesting that the major risk factors include poor glycemic control, obesity, long disease duration, and medication non-adherence.

The most frequent complaint, according to the analysis of self-reported symptoms using TCNS was pain that was present in 67.0% in the right leg and 57.3% in the left leg, followed by tingling which was present for 25.6% in the right leg and 18.5% in the left leg. Numbness was reported by 14.5% in the right leg and 11.5% in the left leg and ataxia was present in 47.1% in the right side and 42.7% in the left side. Weakness was reported

relatively equally in both limbs indicating symmetrical motor involvement. Upper Limb Symptoms was present in only 2.2% in the right arm and 2% in the left arm.

On assessment of reflexes, knee reflex is reduced in 3.1% in the right leg and 3.5% in the left leg and absent in 0 patients, while ankle reflex is reduced in 15.9% in the right leg and 10.1% in the left leg but is absent in 0 patients. Sensory assessment showed light touch sensation to be abnormal for 75.3% in the right leg and 69.6% in the left leg followed by vibration sensation that is abnormal for 73.6% in the right leg and 70.9% in the left leg. Pin prick sensation is abnormal for 32.6% in the right leg and 25.1% in the left leg while temperature sensation is abnormal for 13.2% the right leg and 9.7% in the left leg. Position sense is bilaterally abnormal in 0.4%.

The 51% that patients were observed with diabetes were assessed using TCNS which showed that 61.2 % patients had neuropathy, in which Mild Neuropathy is seen in 16.3% patients, Moderate Neuropathy is seen in 18.5% patients and Severe Neuropathy is seen in 26.4% patients.

Table 1: Neuropathy Distribution

Neuropathy Classification	Scoring	Count	Percentage
No Neuropathy	(0 - 5)	88	38.80%
Mild Neuropathy	(6 - 8)	37	16.30%
Moderate Neuropathy	(9 - 11)	42	18.50%
Severe Neuropathy	(12+)	60	26.40%

Graph 1: Neuropathy Scoring

Among 156 participants that were not on regular medication, 15 had no neuropathy, 17 had mild neuropathy, 23 had moderate neuropathy and 47 had severe neuropathy, while from the 125 participants that were on regular medication, 73 had no neuropathy, 20 had mild neuropathy, 19 had moderate neuropathy and 13 had severe neuropathy.

DISCUSSION:

This study aimed to evaluate diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) in a diabetic population in Pune using the Toronto Clinical Scoring System (TCSS). The analysis of 227 patients reveals a high prevalence of DPN, characterized by significant severity, and strong associations with poor glycemic control caused by not adhering to the medication regimen.

The cohort had a mean age of 60.49 years, with a majority (55%) developing diabetes in the 47-52 age group showing that increasing age is independently associated with an increased risk of developing peripheral neuropathy in patients with T2DM. The population was almost equally split by gender (51% Female, 49% Male). Critically, the cohort exhibited major risk factors for complications: a high BMI (Mean BMI: 27.87 kg/m², indicating an overweight population), a long known duration of diabetes (Mean years: 10.96 years), and poor glycemic control (Mean RBG: 204.31 mg/dl).

The anthropometric analysis revealed that 71% of the participants were either obese or overweight signifying the role of adiposity and insulin resistance in the acceleration of microvascular dysfunction. Patients with T2DM are mostly observed to be obese or have a higher body fat percentage, distributed predominantly in the abdominal region. Adipose tissue promotes insulin resistance through various inflammatory mechanisms, including increased free fatty acid (FFA) release and adipokine deregulation. Chronic hyperglycemia and dislipidemia impairs nitric oxide- mediated vasodilatation, leading to capillary basement membrane thickening and endoneurial hypoxia which collectively precipitate axonal degeneration. The main drivers of the T2DM epidemic are the global rise in obesity, sedentary lifestyles, high caloric diets and population aging, which have quadrupled the incidence and prevalence of T2DM,^[18]

Healthy nerves receive a rich supply of blood from the neural microvasculature, otherwise known as the vasa nervorum. There is an interrelationship between the neural tissues of the nerve axons and the surrounding microvasculature. During DPN, vascular

changes include increased permeability, increased vasoconstriction, and decreased blood flow, which in turn appear to cause motor and sensory-nerve-fibre degeneration.

The disease arises from a combination of microvascular and neuronal deficits. **Metabolic injury** (polyol pathway activation, advanced glycation end-products → oxidative stress), **Microvascular ischemia** (damage to vasa nervorum → nerve hypoxia) and **Inflammatory damage** (cytokine-mediated neuroinflammation).

Oxidative stress can contribute significantly to the deficits as a direct result of prolonged hyperglycemia. These pathways always trigger damage through expression of inflammation proteins which leads to impaired neural function and finally apoptosis of neurons, Schwann and glial cells of peripheral nervous system. Endoneurial hypoxemia caused by impaired endoneurial blood flow contributes to impaired nerve perfusion and further leads to nerve dysfunction. Combination of direct axonal injury due to the metabolic consequences of hyperglycemic insulin resistance, toxic adiposity, endothelial injury and microvascular dysfunctions leads to nerve ischemia.

Diabetes causes functional deficits in nitric oxide (NO) and alterations in endothelial derived relaxing factor (EDRF) resulting in microvascular reactivity and structural microangiopathy, which adds to the worsening of DPN. Functional abnormalities like slowing of sensory nerve conduction velocity (SNCV) and motor nerve conduction velocity (MNCV), hyperalgesia and allodynia are found to develop in early months of inception of hyperglycemia. As the disease progresses, signs of axonopathy, demyelination, nerve degeneration and hypoalgesia can be detected.

The development of DPN is insidious, usually beginning in the toes and under the feet, and then gradually ascends up the leg. Once it is well established in the lower limbs, the upper limbs are affected, with sensory loss following the typical 'glove and stocking' pattern of distribution. It has been observed that the most common early symptoms in DPN show early involvement of the small nerve fibers. Small-fiber involvement is usually painful, with selective loss of pain and temperature sensations. The neuronal damage is then proposed to progress and include large-fibers causing dysfunction in them which is characterized by numbness (feeling as if "walking on wool" or "the foot is wrapped in paper"). With large-fiber dysfunction, gait is insecure, either wide-based or high stepping, which holds an

increased risk of fall. In DPN, small and large fiber dysfunction most commonly coexist, with a combinations of symptoms while clinical presentation, such as numbness, painful sensations, gait abnormalities and postural instability.

Symptoms:

Pain is the most prevalent symptom, affecting 67.0% in the right leg and 57.3% in the left leg. Small myelinated A δ fibers (sharp pain) and unmyelinated C fibers (burning pain) carry pain sensation through the spinothalamic tract. Small fibers are damaged by oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and Na⁺ channel upregulation. Damaged nociceptors fire ectopically causing burning, shooting, or stabbing pain. Ion-channel dysregulation causes up-regulation or redistribution of voltage-gated sodium channels (e.g., Nav1.7, Nav1.8) and changes in calcium/potassium channels in damaged sensory neurons. This lowers the threshold for activation, causing hyperexcitability. Injured nerves release inflammatory mediators (e.g., TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6), prostaglandins, bradykinin, etc., which sensitize nociceptors (pain-sensing fibres). Burning pain is especially linked to C-fibre dysfunction (slow, unmyelinated fibres) and their abnormal activity. The slow conduction, poor repair, and high metabolic demand make C-fibres vulnerable.^[20,21,22,23]

Tingling affected 25.6% in the right leg and 18.5% in the left leg, **Small sensory fibres** (thinly-myelinated A δ and unmyelinated C fibres) carry sensations such as pain, temperature, and also contribute to tingling/paresthesia. When these are injured or become hyperactive they can create “pins & needles” (tingling) or burning sensations.

Numbness is reported by 14.5% in the right leg and 11.5% in the left leg. **Large sensory fibres** (myelinated A β fibres) carry vibration, proprioception, touch and pressure. When these fibres are damaged, patients develop **numbness** (loss of sensation) and loss of protective sensation. Because protective sensation is lost (numbness), patients are at increased risk of foot injury and ulceration.

Weakness was reported relatively equally in both limbs 38.3% in right leg and 37.9% in left leg indicating symmetrical motor involvement. Muscle strength decreases with age; especially after the age of 60 years, there is considerable and accelerated loss. Motor dysfunction can be caused by muscle weakness and atrophy of muscular tissue which is found distally in the extremities, primarily in the lower extremities. This motor impairment is known to be caused by diabetic neuropathy.^[24]

Ataxia was observed in 47.1% participants in the right side and 42.7% in the left side. Loss or reduction of ankle reflexes, decreased position and vibratory senses and sensory ataxia are present. Proper gait, stance and coordination rely heavily on feedback from proprioceptive and vibration-sensing peripheral nerves. When these fibres are damaged, the brain and spinal cord no longer receive accurate information about limb position and movement and thus instable gait is observed. Although sensory fibre loss is the main driver of ataxia, in advanced DPN there may be some motor involvement (foot intrinsic muscle wasting, weakness) which further impairs stability and gait.^[25,26]

Upper Limb Symptoms show a notably low prevalence 2.2% in the right hand and 2% in the left hand, confirming the primarily lower-limb distribution characteristic of diabetic peripheral neuropathy. DPN is typically **length-dependent** where the longest nerves (to the feet) are affected first. As the disease progresses, more proximal and shorter nerves (including those to the hands) become involved. These patterns align with findings from Brill and Perkins (2002), validating the diagnostic sensitivity of TCSS for mixed- fiber neuropathies.

Reflex integrity:

Ankle Reflexes demonstrated significant impairment, with a reduction observed in 15.90% of right ankles and 10.10% of left ankles while knee reflexes were largely preserved, with minimal involvement of **Knee Reflexes** 3.10% in the right leg and 3.50% in the left. Reflex arcs depend on large, myelinated afferent (sensory) fibres ($A\alpha/A\beta$) from muscle spindles, tendon stretch receptors, and large efferent (motor) fibres. These fibres are vulnerable in DPN. DPN typically begins in the longest axons (feet/legs) because they are more vulnerable to metabolic and ischemic injury. This progressive loss of distal tendon reflexes reflect the length-dependent nature of diabetic neuropathy in which the longest nerves are most vulnerable to the metabolic injury thereby affecting the distal reflexes (ankle) to go firstly followed by the proximal reflexes (knee) as these reflex arc requires intact conduction and proper synaptic input while damage compromises their integrity.^[27,28]

Sensations Affected:

Cutaneous and deep sensations are mediated by superficial and deep topically distributed receptors and nerve fibers. Touch-pressure sensation is mediated by Meissner corpuscles with small receptive fields, sharp borders, and low thresholds that accommodate rapidly. Pacinian corpuscles respond to vibratory stimuli and have large receptive fields with sloping borders

and low thresholds that accommodate quickly. Cooling receptors are more frequent and widely distributed than warm receptors. [19]

Pin-Prick sensation was affected in 32.60% on the right foot and 25.10% on the left foot. Pin-prick sensation is transmitted primarily by small myelinated A δ fibres and unmyelinated C fibres through the spinothalamic tract. Because the small-fibre input is lost or impaired, the patient cannot feel sharp stimuli (pin-prick) in the affected areas. Moreover, as fibre density decreases (e.g., in skin biopsy studies showing reduced intra-epidermal nerve fibre density), the threshold for nociceptive stimuli rises and eventually may fail entirely. Loss of pin-prick sensation indicates small-fibre involvement and loss of protective nociception. This increases risk of unnoticed injuries, foot ulcers and complications. [29]

Temperature sensation was affected in 13.20% on the right and 9.70% on the left foot. Temperature sensation is carried by A δ (cold) and C (warm) fibers via the spinothalamic tract. Same small fibers that carry pain signals also mediate temperature. Because these fibres are damaged by the same mechanisms (metabolic injury, ischemia, loss of intraepidermal nerve-fibres) axonal loss and demyelination is observed which leads to impaired thermal sensation. Clinically this means patients may not sense extremes of temperature, increasing risk of burns or injuries. [30]

Light Touch Sensation is abnormal in 75.3% in the Right leg and 69.6% in the left leg. Touch sensation is carried by large myelinated A β fibers through dorsal column–medial lemniscus tract. These fibres have high metabolic demand, long axonal lengths (especially to the feet) and rely on intact myelin and vascular supply. In DPN, metabolic and vascular insults compromise axonal transport and myelin integrity that cause slowed conduction and eventual loss of these fibres. For example, large-fibre damage contributes to loss of protective tactile sensation. This results clinically in reduced or absent light touch/pressure sensing, increasing risk of foot injury. [31]

Vibration Sensation is Abnormal in 73.6% in the right leg and 70.9% in the left leg. Vibration sensation is mediated by **large myelinated A β fibers**. These **large fibers** are **more metabolically active** and **depend heavily on oxygen and nutrient supply** from the **vasa nervorum**. Chronic hyperglycemia causes **microvascular ischemia and metabolic injury**, making these fibers **especially vulnerable** early in DPN. Because vibration fibres are long and large, their distal ends are earliest exposed to damage. [32]

Proprioception was abnormal in only 0.4% bilaterally. Position sensation is carried by large myelinated A β fibers by the dorsal column–medial lemniscus and also by muscle spindle afferents (large fibres). Large-fibre degeneration (as above) impairs proprioceptive input but joint position sense is often spared until very advanced stages of disease. Loss of position sense contributes to unsteady gait, ataxia, and increased fall risk.

The high percentage of abnormalities in light touch (75.3%) and vibration sensation (73.6%) are classic signs of large-fiber neuropathy, which directly contributes to loss of protective sensation and balance problems (ataxia). Pinprick and temperature (small-fiber functions) were affected to a lesser but still significant degree. Ankle reflexes were reduced in about 3-16% of patients, a common early sign in DPN. Knee reflexes were largely preserved.

Patients not on regular medication had a dramatically higher prevalence of DPN (85.3%) and severe neuropathy (46%) compared to those on medication (DPN: 41.6%, Severe neuropathy: 11%). Regular medication adherence is a powerful protective factor, associated with a more than 50% reduction in overall DPN risk and a 77% reduction in the risk of severe neuropathy. Regular medication, likely aimed at controlling blood glucose and other metabolic parameters, appears to be a key protective factor against the development and progression of nerve damage. The finding that nearly half of the non-adherent patients have severe neuropathy highlights a high-risk subgroup that requires immediate and targeted intervention. This emphasizes that improving medication adherence is not just about glycemic control but is directly linked to preventing debilitating complications. Moreover, it reinforces the protective role of consistent pharmacology glycemic control and aligns with Zilliox et al (2005), who demonstrated that sustained glucose management delays neuropathy onset.

The finding that 61.2% of patients have DPN is substantially higher than many previous estimates, indicating a severe local burden. The fact that severe neuropathy (26.4%) is more prevalent than mild (16.3%) or moderate (18.5%) categories suggests that neuropathy is often undiagnosed, untreated, or progresses rapidly in this population, leading to a large cohort at immediate risk for foot ulcers and amputations.

The neuropathy severity classification reveals a diabetic population with substantial neurological burden, where nearly two-thirds of patients exhibit detectable neuropathy and

over one-quarter present with severe, high-risk disease. This distribution highlights critical gaps in current diabetes management strategies and emphasizes the urgent need for implementing systematic TCSS-based screening protocols. The findings strongly support early intervention strategies targeting patients with mild-to-moderate neuropathy to prevent progression to severe, debilitating disease and its devastating complications. The results underscore the value of the Toronto Clinical Scoring System as an effective tool for risk stratification and management planning in diabetic peripheral neuropathy.

This comprehensive assessment establishes a concerning burden of diabetic peripheral neuropathy in Pune's urban diabetic population. The findings demonstrate the complex interplay between metabolic factors, disease duration, and clinical presentation of neuropathy. The Toronto Clinical Scoring System emerges as an effective tool for routine clinical assessment, while the identified risk factors provide clear targets for public health interventions. These results emphasize the critical need for integrating systematic neuropathy screening and preventive foot care into standard diabetes management protocols to reduce the significant morbidity associated with this complication.

In summary, the findings highlight that long disease duration, poor glycemic control, obesity and medication non-compliance are the major determinants of neuropathy severity. These results emphasize the necessity for early TCSS based screening and multidisciplinary management including physiotherapy, nutrition and endocrinology collaboration to mitigate progression towards ulceration and amputation.

CONCLUSION:

This study concludes that diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is highly prevalent (61.2%) among diabetic patients in Pune, with severe neuropathy affecting 26.4%. Major risk factors include poor glycemic control, obesity, long disease duration, and medication non-adherence. The Toronto Clinical Scoring System emerges as an effective tool for routine clinical assessment, while the identified risk factors provide clear targets for public health interventions. Findings highlight that metabolic and microvascular injury underlie neuropathic damage, emphasizing the need for early TCSS-based screening, strict glycemic control, and multidisciplinary management involving endocrinology, physiotherapy, and nutrition to prevent progression, ulceration, and amputations in high-risk diabetic individuals.

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